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SatWind

Final Report

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Preface

The Norwegian coastal line, extending 21,465 km, is one of the longest national coasts in Europe. Recently, the Norwegian government has expressed interest in developing windmill parks along the Norwegian coast. A few smaller sites have already been developed, while one of the most suitable parts of this long coastal zone, the Norwegian west coast, still does not host any wind mill parks. The area considered the Norwegian West Coast is indicated within the blue rectangle in the figure below. One of the most important factors for cost efficient windmill development is the existence of infrastructure (road and power line network). This makes the part of the Norwegian West Coast located close to Norway's second largest city, Bergen, of particular interest for windmill developers and power companies. This region is illustrated with the red rectangle in the figure below.

Map of Norway with the West Coast (blue rectangle) and main area of interest for windmill development (red rectangle) annotated.

For this CEO funded SatWind project, the area of interest for product tuning and marketing, identical to the region market in red in the figure above, was selected based on its importance for near future wind mill park development and in-house Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data availability. The SatWind products tuned and marketed in this CEO funded project thus only covers this region. This region fits approximately within one SAR scene of 100 by 100 km. This product thus obviously covers only a small part of the total Norwegian coastline, and not even all of the Norwegian West Coast. However, this 100 km stretch along the region west of Bergen is one of the most interesting regions for wind mill park development. Thus, the number of potential customers is relatively large, and also includes companies, institutes and public offices with not only regional, but also national and international interests. These are the reasons why this region, market with a red rectangle in the figure above, was selected for the SatWind products developed and marketed during this study. However, the method developed is general and can be transferred to other parts of the Norwegian coast, as well as European coasts. More details on the study area and its potential customers are described in this report.

SUMMARY

The Earth's population is facing an increasing demand for electrical power. After the Koyoto meeting which gave clear signals of reductions in the CO₂ emission to the atmosphere it is clear that new alternative sources of power must be considered to meet those needs. In this context it has been focused on possibilities for increasing the utilization of converting wind energy into electrical power by use of wind mills. With the technical improvement of wind power turbines in recent years, operating wind power-plants have become more economically efficient, and is today a full-worthy source for complementing other types of energy. As an example 7% of the Danish power consumption supplying about 200.000 households are wind generated.

In planning for wind mill park installations it is of fundamental importance to have sufficient information about the wind characteristics for different wind conditions. Standard wind measurements are available from ground mounted instruments, such as cup- or sonic anemometers which usually provides time series of averaged 1 or 10 minutes intervals. Such measurements are very local and will not properly resolve the spatial variations in the wind field and it is thus generally difficult to estimate wind conditions at a nearby site. Since one from atmospheric boundary layer meteorology know that the surface wind field will have large spatial variations, mapping of the wind field with high spatial resolution will be of great importance for wind mill siting.

Satellite based Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) measurements so far from ERS 1 / ERS-2 have been shown to provide wind speed data with an accuracy of ± 2 m/s. The SAR has clear advantages for high spatial resolution wind field mapping since it is independent of daylight and clouds. Wind retrieval from SAR will become very important from year 2000, since ENVISAT will carry SAR (which provide wind fields over 500 km swaths), but no wind scatterometer. Wind maps generated from SAR will be able to provide spatial information about the wind with a resolution of 400 m. These wind data can be used to derive wind energy maps for coastal regions, as first suggested by Johannessen and Bjørgo ("Wind energy mapping of coastal zones by SAR for siting potential wind mill locations", Int. J. Remote Sensing, in press 1999). This report describes a SAR wind energy product to be used in wind mill siting.

The traditional current performance of products used to map wind conditions in coastal areas are mainly based on in situ point measurements and mathematical modelling. *SatWind*, the product developed here, can not be directly compared to existing methods, as the product covers larger regions with continuous spatial information, and not point-data as traditional wind-measurements provide. The consortium behind *SatWind* is Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), and its commercial subsidiary, TerraOrbit Ltd.

The targeted customers represent private industry and public agencies involved in wind power-plant development. We also intend to market the product towards interest-organisations, such as Western Norway Wind-Power Forum, and the Norwegian Wind-Power Forum. In general, the market consists of all companies, and agencies, in need of wind-information in coastal areas. However, for the specific *SatWind* product developed here, these are limited to customers whose primary interest is wind power development along the Norwegian west coast.

These customers need reliable data to locate optimum sites for placing individual wind mills, but also information to develop policies for where to limit construction due to e.g. wildlife parks, or strong environmental impacts. Based on the market survey it is clear that the customers need spatially continuous information on wind conditions. However, based on the cost-analysis it is clear that the product must fit into the rather limited budget used for wind information. The market segment will therefore be targeted with the above described SatWind1 and SatWind2 products. Based on the percentage of wind situations the customer wants to cover, SatWind2 is split into SatWind2A (covering three typical wind situations) and SatWind2B (covering five typical wind situations).

SatWind1 is designed to provide individual users, foremost private companies, with synergy information to the data they already have (in situ point measurements and/or modeling results). The interactive digital part of the product will improve quantification means and further demonstrate SatWinds usefulness as a synergy product. SatWind2 is intended more towards users who can afford a more expensive product, such as governmental agencies and major private companies. The added information compared to SatWind1 will be examples of various wind situations, listed as very important by the users themselves in the market-survey. Three or five images of various wind conditions, including one from the annual typical case, also provided as SatWind1. The price of SatWind1 will be Euro 500. SatWind2A is priced to Euro 3,600 and SatWind2B to Euro 6,000. These prices are based on full cost for development of each product. All customers must sign a licence agreement with TerraOrbit, prohibiting copying and distribution of the product, unless specifically agreed.

An optimal wind speed estimate from the so-called C band models depends on the radiometric capabilities of the SAR to reproduce the normalized radar cross section (NRCS). An accurate calibration of the raw SAR data is necessary, and this is performed according to specifications given by *Laur et al.* [1997]. In particular the images are corrected for analogue-to-digital (ADC) conversation power loss. This power loss is caused by saturation in the binary representation of the radar signal and it is important to correct for this in cases of high radar return, i.e. high wind speed, in the image.

The wind speed is retrieved from the radar backscatter using a C band model. The CMOD IF2, developed at the Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer (IFREMER), is today used operationally for retrieval of wind field from the ERS-2 Wind Scatterometer (WSC). CMOD IF2 is empirically tuned to in situ measurements, and retrieves the wind field with an uncertainty of ± 2 m/s in wind speed and $\pm 20^\circ$ in the wind direction for the WSC. The CMOD IF2 has been shown to be applicable to the SAR with the same uncertainty on wind speed down to a resolution of at least 400 m. A disadvantage of the SAR is the wind direction that is needed as an input to the model. The wind direction can in approximately 50% of the cases be estimated from signatures in the SAR image. These signatures can be lee effects of land or signatures of atmospheric roll vortices or Langmuir cells. In other cases the wind direction can be taken from meteorological weather stations along the coast, or from the Hindcast database of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute, or any other local wind models. It should be noted that an error in wind direction of 90° , which is the worst case, will result in an error in wind speed of 2 m/s for low winds and up to more than 10 m/s for strong winds. However, for strong winds the variation in local wind direction is little and in almost all these cases it is possible to locally verify the measured wind direction with signatures in the SAR images.

The examples of a product described in this report are taken from a region covering south-western Norway. This was due to the fact that we already possessed several SAR scenes from this region. However, the methodology is transferable to other regions, for potential expansion of the product in the future.

The ideal situation is to be able to use the SAR imagery to retrieve the spatial variation of the probability density function (PDF) of the wind speed. However, this cannot be retrieved from a limited number of SAR images such as will be used in the products SatWind1 and SatWind2. Therefore, local meteorological data (wind roses) have to be used to find days with typical wind directions and speeds. Corresponding SAR images will then give examples of spatial wind variations for such a (typical) day. This is a limitation of the SAR, and is also partly due to data cost.

The developed product will be offered together with descriptions on the processing procedure, and limitations of the technology. Based on the market survey and results from the workshop, it is the conclusion that SatWind has commercial value, and the product will be marketed and promoted starting in the summer of 1999. An interactive version of the product is provided to the customers at the web-site <http://sofia.nrsc.no>.

1. Introduction

Background

The current performance of products used to map wind conditions in coastal areas are mainly based on in situ point measurements and mathematical modelling. SatWind can not be directly compared to existing methods, as the product covers larger regions with continuous spatial information, and not point-data as traditional wind-measurements provide. The consortium behind SatWind is Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), and its commercial subsidiary, TerraOrbit Ltd.

Satellite based Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) measurements so far from ERS 1 / ERS-2 have been shown to provide wind speed data with an accuracy of ± 2 m/s. The SAR has clear advantages for high spatial resolution wind field mapping since it is independent of daylight and clouds. Wind retrieval from SAR will become very important from year 2000, since ENVISAT will carry SAR (which provide wind fields over 500 km swaths), but no wind scatterometer. Wind maps generated from SAR will be able to provide spatial information about the wind with a resolution of 400 m. These wind data can be used to derive wind energy maps for coastal regions. This report describes a SAR wind energy product to be used in wind mill siting.

Based on data from the Danish wind turbine association (www.windpower.dk), total global wind turbine sales for 1997 was approximately Euro 700 million. The main cost of setting up a wind mill is the turbine. A quality product would thus have a relatively large market to operate in, even if the costs related to wind mapping are relatively modest (1-3% of total project budget).

Rationale

The Earth's population is facing an increasing demand for electrical power. After the Koyoto meeting which gave clear signals of reductions in the CO₂ emission to the atmosphere it is clear that new alternative sources of power must be considered to meet those needs. In this context it has been focused on possibilities for increasing the utilization of converting wind energy into electrical power by use of wind mills. With the technical improvement of wind power turbines in recent years, operating wind power-plants have become more economically efficient, and is today a full-worthy source for complementing other types of energy. As an example 7% of the Danish power consumption supplying about 200.000 households are wind generated.

In planning for wind mill park installations it is of fundamental importance to have sufficient information about the wind characteristics for different wind conditions. Standard wind measurements are available from ground mounted instruments, such as cup- or sonic anemometers which usually provides time series of averaged 1 or 10 minutes intervals. Such measurements are very local and will not properly resolve the spatial variations in the wind field and it is thus generally difficult to estimate wind conditions at a nearby site. Since one from atmospheric boundary layer meteorology know that the surface wind field will have large spatial variations, mapping of the wind field with high spatial resolution will be of great importance for wind mill siting.

In our studies of high spatial variations in the wind energy along the coast line we investigated how to use high resolution Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) measurements from the European ERS-1&2 satellites. The instrument have their clear advantages in being able to operate under all atmospheric conditions and are independent of daylight and clouds. The SAR spatial resolution of ~30m is more than sufficient for the application presented here as is the temporal coverage of potential wind mill park sites. The concept of using SAR in wind energy mapping for planning of wind mill siting was recently published by Johannessen and Korsbakken (1998).

Wind mill parks can also be important to the meet energy demands in developing countries. In these areas where the infrastructure is limited regarding power distribution systems, local wind mill parks can be an efficient way to provide sustainable power. In these regions, SAR derived wind information can play a very important role for planning installations regardless of lacking field observations and difficult accessible areas.

Figure 1.1. Off-shore wind mill park in Vindeby, Denmark.

An important aspect of wind mill siting is including the potential for off-shore wind mill parks, see Figure 1.1. Several parks are already constructed, e.g. Vindeby and Tunø Knob in Denmark, and more are in the planning phase. Many countries lack suitable land-based wind mill sites, and moving the wind-turbines off shore is therefore more appropriate. Just as important is the fact that wind speeds are often higher off-shore than on-shore, differences of 20% within a small area on/off shore are not uncommon (S. Krohn, www.windpower.dk). An important aspect in mapping coastal wind-energy areas from satellite is the advantage of combining the continuous spatial coverage with equally spatial continuous datasets of ocean bathymetry, i.e. ocean depth. Obviously off-shore wind installations will need to be located in relatively shallow areas the keep the construction costs as low as possible. Databases on wildlife, and plant habitats can also be included in such studies. Combining information in a Marine or Coastal GIS system can be a powerful tool for locating optimal sites for off-shore wind mill parks.

The methods developed here can also prove valuable for mapping coastal wind energy potential on a global scale. A cost-efficient method for mapping this valuable renewable energy source has the potential to be adopted by international organizations, foreign governments as well as private companies. Wind energy mapping from satellite has the potential to be an important export product for our company TerraOrbit Ltd.

2. Work Methodology

The general approach for this product has been to customise already existing methods for deriving wind-speed based on satellite SAR imagery. The work carried out in this process has been two-fold: The first part consisted of developing and tuning the proposed product to a practical, user-friendly product, SatWind. This work was carried out by the Nansen Center, and is described in detail in section 4, and appendix 1. The second part of the project has been the development of a marketing plan, including a user survey and workshop. This work was carried out by TerraOrbit. The marketing plan is described in more detail in section 3 and appendix 2.

Below follows a step-by-step description of the tasks carried out in the project.

WP1000: Project management.

NERSC has been the project manager for SatWind. One workshop has been organised. The project has been promoted through various meetings and conferences. NERSC has also been responsible for delivering minutes from the workshop and project meetings, as well as progress reports.

WP2000: Marketing plan

TerraOrbit has been responsible for producing a marketing plan, see appendix 2 for details regarding the marketing plan. This plan has been produced based on a user survey, user workshop and from discussions with representatives from individual organisations. A marketing strategy was proposed based on the findings from the user survey and user workshop. In order to minimise the product cost for the user, but at the same time offer a useful product, the use of SAR scenes has been optimised.

WP3000: Product development

The task leader of this WP has been NERSC. The wind retrieval algorithm is described in the appendix of the technical report, appendix 1. The wind energy maps were made using interactive data programs called IDL, and Matlab. The maps illustrate different wind energies in different red-tones. Examples are shown in the technical report, see appendix 1. The SAR data have also been combined with met. data (wind roses) in the technical report. The product was customized in the best possible way allow the customer to decide for him/herself how many images to buy, based on the percent of wind situations he/she wants to cover. Sample products have been developed and are shown in the technical report, see appendix 1.

WP4000: Demonstration of product

SatWind has been promoted by NERSC and TerraOrbit through various forums, such as participation at meetings and conferences on wind energy, and in scientific and popular science articles. A dedicated web-site has been established, see example below.

Figure 2.1: SatWind web-page located at sofia.nrsc.no.

Demonstration material will be promoted towards customers upon completion of the CEO funded SatWind study.

WP5000: Preparation of final report

This final report has been prepared by NERSC and TerraOrbit. A previous version has been presented to CEO staff. Five copies of the final report will be submitted to CEO.

3. Marketing plan excerpt

The marketing plan is described in detail in appendix 2.

3.1 Market analysis

Market segment

The targeted customers represent private industry and public agencies involved in wind power-plant development. We also intend to market the product towards interest-organisations, such as Western Norway Wind-Power Forum, and the Norwegian Wind-Power Forum. In general, the market consists of all companies, and agencies, in need of wind-information in coastal areas. However, for the specific SatWind product developed here, these are limited to customers whose primary interest is wind power development along the Norwegian west coast.

Needs and profiles

These customers need reliable data to locate optimum sites for placing individual wind mills, but also information to develop policies for where to limit construction due to e.g. wildlife parks, or strong environmental impacts. Based on the market survey it is clear that the customers need spatially continuous information on wind conditions. However, based on the cost-analysis it is clear that the product must fit into the rather limited budget used for wind information. The market segment will therefore be targeted with the SatWind1 and SatWind2A&B products, see appendix 1 and 2 for details.

SatWind1 is designed to provide individual users, foremost private companies, with synergy information to the data they already have (in situ point measurements and/or modelling results). The interactive digital part of the product will improve quantification means and further demonstrate SatWinds usefulness as a synergy product. SatWind2A&B are intended more towards users who can afford a more expensive product, such as governmental agencies and major private companies. The added information compared to SatWind1 will be examples of various wind situations, listed as very important by the users themselves in the market-survey. Three or five images of various wind conditions, including one from the annual typical case, also provided as SatWind1. The price of SatWind1 will be Euro 500. SatWind2A is priced to Euro 3,600, while SatWind2B is priced to Euro 6,000. Break even levels are listed in appendix 2, section 2.2. These prices are based on full cost for development of each product. As for the western Norway product currently offered, the labour has already been done, and so the cost involved will be imagery purchase and hardcopy production. All customers must sign a licence agreement with TerraOrbit, prohibiting copying and distribution of the product, unless specifically agreed.

Market size estimates

From the market analysis, one can not retrieve different patterns in information-requirements from the three different user groups (interest organisations, private companies, governmental agencies). This can possibly be because the development and planning of wind power plants along the Norwegian coast are still in an early phase. It could also be attributed to similar

information needs, and that the developers know that they have to take various environmental aspects into consideration when planning a windmill site.

Based on the market-survey, the potential customers indicate that they use approximately Euro 12,000-25,000 on wind-mapping during the decision-making process on where to locate a wind-mill. This cost varies greatly, but in general it is estimated that the customers use 1-3% of the total budget for collecting information on the wind-conditions. The rule-of-thumb is that the total budget is approximately Euro 900 per kW the wind-mill is designed to deliver.

Given that our product is designed to provide complementary information to point-measurements and mathematical models, it is not realistic that the customers will use more than 25% of their budget on our product, i.e. 25% of the 1-3% spent on wind mapping. The advantages with SatWind have already been described. It is also a new product that might draw attention because the customers simply would like to assess the usefulness of this product themselves. It is thus concluded that the customers can be willing to pay up to Euro 6,000 for a quality product.

Competitor assessment

When compared to our main competitors within the wind energy mapping industry, the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (in situ measurements, turnover for 1998 was approximately Euro 36 million) and Vector AS (the main private topographic modelling company in Norway, turnover for 1998 was approximately Euro 116,000), TerraOrbit's budget and result are comparatively very small. At the moment TerraOrbit has a staff of only one person, but the close cooperation with its owner, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), gives TerraOrbit access to NERSC staff and equipment.

Differential advantage

No other companies provide spatially continuous products of measured wind speed and wind energy over near coastal ocean areas. Accordingly, the provision of continuous spatial information is the main advantage of our product. The maps can also relatively easily be implemented in GIS in order to assess where there are existing road networks and power transport infrastructure. Such parameters are included in one of our competitors products (topographic modeling results overlaid road networks). These are important parameters to keep the investments low and thus potential profits higher for the power-plant companies.

However, two major competitors, The Norwegian Meteorological Institute, and Vector Ltd., provide in situ and modelling data for wind speed estimates. These competitors are likely to continue providing local information on wind speed conditions. It is the intention that SatWind is used in synergy with these in situ and modelling products to complement the overall information requirements.

We will focus on the synergy effect with point-measures and that our product can show relatively large local variations in this coastal area. We thus want the customers to choose our product as an add-on to existing products, but used so as to maximise the potential benefit in choosing one location instead of another. Point-measurements can never be replaced, but in deciding where to put them, our product can be beneficial. Another benefit is that our product can be provided within a relatively short time frame. Since the products are pre-defined, SatWind1 and SatWind2, these

can be delivered to the customers within 24 hours, or within two days if the existing stock of hardcopies and CD-ROMs is empty. This is a differential advantage when assessing an area where no point measurements are available. In situ data are normally collected over one year, see market-survey, and so our low-level product will have a differential advantage in such areas.

Another differential advantage will be the easy-to-use interactive interface. The user interface will be through an HTML coded website and CD-ROM and so energy profiles will be extracted without much technical know-how on how to integrate the energy and plot this in a separate software program. SatWind will be user friendly. This is especially important when the customers are e.g. politicians, bureaucrats, and land owners without expertise knowledge in wind mapping.

3.2 Exploitation plan

Launch and distribution

SatWind1 will be provided as a single-licence product only, while SatWind2A&B will be provided with a multi-licence. SatWind1 is thus targeted towards private companies, while SatWind2A&B are targeted towards interest organisations and governmental agencies. To each of the products, a technical support service is included. The product will be officially launched on 1 September after acceptance of the final report and preparation for coordinated press release and information on web-site.

The product will be distributed in hardcopy form including wind-speed and –energy images, in combination with technical descriptions about the product. In addition, the user will also receive a CD-ROM with the image and text in digital form. Furthermore, an interactive web-based password protected application has been developed for both products. User-name and password is supplied with the product order confirmation. The customers can inter-actively define a section of interest, and then immediately view the distribution of wind-speed and –energy variations along the section. The Internet address for the interactive-application is <http://sofia.nrsc.no>.

Marketing and promotion

SatWind will be marketed and promoted by TerraOrbit Ltd. The goal is to market the product towards all key players in the wind-energy business along the west coast of Norway, offices involved in wind-power policy, as well as other key players in the wind-energy business operating elsewhere. An additional goal is to promote the product within national governmental agencies, such as the Ministry of Oil and Energy, and the Ministry of Environment.

A total number of 41 potential customers (targets for promotion activities) have been identified. These are listed in Appendix A.

During the first year, TerraOrbit will actively market the product towards potential users of the product for western Norway. From year 2 and beyond, active marketing towards wind power developers, in particular off-shore sites, will be undertaken. These include coastal areas of the UK, Denmark, Germany, France, Portugal, and Italy.

SatWind has been promoted through:

- a newsstory on national TV (TV2, 22 March 1998).
- in various newspapers:
 - Aftenposten 17 March 1998, Aftenposten is the largest subscription newspaper and the third largest single copies newspaper in Norway. Circulation number: approximately 500 000
 - Bergensavisen 18 March 1998, circulation number approximately 31 000
- a talk given at a conference for the regional wind-power industry (Vindkraftforum Vest), 9 February (28 participants)
- a poster presentation at a conference for the national wind-power industry (Norsk Vindkraftforum) 17 February. This conference was attended by 42 people, and the secretary for the minister of oil&energy was a keynote speaker.
- a workshop for potential users was held at the Nansen Centers premises on 26 April.
- A scientific article on the methodology has also been accepted for publication as a cover story in International Journal of Remote Sensing.
- Product information also is accessible through TerraOrbits web-site: www.terraorbit.com.
- The final product will be featured in advertisements in special wind energy magazines and by direct marketing towards all identified potential customers. Moreover, copies of the news-video, newspaper articles and the scientific article will be sent potential customers accompanied by a detailed description of the product.

4. Tailored product description

More details on the technical product description can be found in appendix 1.

Satellite based Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) measurements so far from ERS 1 / ERS-2 have been shown to provide wind speed data with an accuracy of ± 2 m/s. The SAR has clear advantages for high spatial resolution wind field mapping since it is independent of daylight and clouds. Wind retrieval from SAR will become very important from year 2000, since ENVISAT will carry SAR (which provide wind fields over 500 km swaths), but no wind scatterometer. Wind maps generated from SAR will be able to provide spatial information about the wind with a **resolution of 400 m**. These wind data can be used to derive wind energy maps for coastal regions. This report describes a first version of a SAR wind energy product (including its limitations), to be used in wind mill siting.

Example of a customer request

If a customer, interested in building a wind mill park, requests e.g. the SatWind1 product for a specific region, the following steps will be taken:

1. The wind rose from the local weather station will be ordered.
2. The most typical wind direction and corresponding wind speed is found.
3. Weather maps and hindcast data are ordered.
4. One day with SAR coverage corresponding to the typical weather situation is found.
5. The SAR image from this day is ordered.
6. The SAR image is then analysed together with the weather data. The SAR image is displayed both as a wind speed map and a wind energy map. The wind speed extracted from the SAR image (in 10×10 km and a 20×20 km boxes) are compared against the measured wind speed. Comments are made on the spatial variability of the wind in the SAR image. Comments can also be made on the time(s) of year and large-scale weather situations for these situations to occur.

See appendix 1 for the resulting products.

References

Furevik, B., and Korsbakken, E., Comparison of Synthetic Aperture Radar and Scatterometer derived wind speed during the ERS Tandem Phase, Submitted to J. Geophys. Res., May 1999.

Laur, H., P. Bally, P. Meadows, P. J. Sanchez, B. Schaettler, E. Lopinto, Derivation of the backscattering coefficient σ_0 in ESA ERS SAR PRI products, Doc. *ES-TN-RS-PM-HL09*, issue 2, rev. 2, Eur. Space Res. Inst., Frascati, Italy, June 28, 1996.

Quilfen, Y., ERS-1 off-line wind scatterometer products, Technical report, Doc. *CI-EX-MUT-CD0000-03-IF*, issue 1.0, IFREMER, BP 70, 29280 Plouzane, France, 1995.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

Market knowledge

According to the users present at the workshop, SatWind1 and SatWind2A&B are of commercial interest, in spite of the lack of temporal averaging. Since SAR imagery is a simple snapshot of the wind conditions acquired during similar times of day (ascending/descending passes), NERSC and TerraOrbit will select the imagery closest to these situations. This was acceptable by the users present. The representative from the Norwegian Wind Power Association also pointed out that the standard meteorological stations should not always be assumed correct, and the additional information provided by the snapshot SAR imagery derived products would be of interest. The identification and visualisation of e.g. wind fronts and turbulent areas would be of high interest for the users, according to this representative for the Norwegian Wind Power Association. The users thus found the relative (as opposed to absolute) information to be of commercial value.

Since SatWind1 and SatWind2A&B will present a spatial continuous snapshot of a near annual average wind situation (SatWind 1), as well as three or five typical wind situations (SatWind2A&B) the typical features possible to extract have commercial value, according to the users present.

The developed product will be offered together with descriptions on the processing procedure, and limitations of the technology. Based on the market survey and results from the workshop, it is the conclusion that SatWind has commercial value, and the product will be marketed and promoted as described in this document.

Appendix 1: Technical Report

SATWIND

Final technical report

by

Heidi A. Espedal and Birgitte Furevik

30 July, 1999

1. Validation

Satellite based Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) measurements so far from ERS 1 / ERS-2 have been shown to provide wind speed data with an accuracy of ± 2 m/s. The SAR has clear advantages for high spatial resolution wind field mapping since it is independent of daylight and clouds. Wind retrieval from SAR will become very important from year 2000, since ENVISAT will carry SAR (which provide wind fields over 500 km swaths), but no wind scatterometer. Wind maps generated from SAR will be able to provide spatial information about the wind with a **resolution of 400 m**. These wind data can be used to derive wind energy maps for coastal regions. This report describes a first version of a SAR wind energy product (including its limitations), to be used in wind mill siting.

2. Example of a customer request

If a customer, interested in building a wind mill park, requests e.g. the SatWind1 product for a specific region, the following steps will be taken:

- The wind rose from the local weather station will be ordered.
- The most typical wind direction and corresponding wind speed is found.
- Weather maps and hindcast data are ordered.
- One day with SAR coverage corresponding to the typical weather situation is found.
- The SAR image from this day is ordered.
- The SAR image is then analysed together with the weather data. The SAR image is displayed both as a wind speed map and a wind energy map. The wind speed extracted from the SAR image (in 10×10 km and a 20×20 km boxes) are compared against the measured wind speed. Comments are made on the spatial variability of the wind in the SAR image. Comments can also be made on the time(s) of year and large-scale weather situations for these situation to occur.

An example of the procedure is shown in below, for a region covering Hellisøy, on the southwestern coast of Norway.

3. The SatWind products

The SatWind1 and SatWind2 products are as follows:

- SatWind1: From local wind roses the most typical wind direction and speed is obtained. A day with such conditions are found from the hindcast data or weather maps. The corresponding SAR image is obtained and analysed. An example product is described below.
- SatWind2 (A and B): From local wind roses three-to-five different typical wind directions and corresponding speeds are obtained. These should cover about 70% of the typical wind directions. The customer may be given an option of the number of images, depending on the

frequency of wind direction occurrence to be covered. Days with such conditions are found from hindcast data or weather maps. The corresponding SAR images are obtained and analysed. An example product is described below .

The products will be delivered both on CD rom and as a hardcopy (the original will be presented on a larger paper than shown in this report. The A3 format will enhance image details).

The SatWind1 product:

The most typical wind direction is found using wind roses from the local weather station. The wind rose from Hellisøy is shown in Fig.1. Winds are predominantly from the south (21.5%) and approximately 5-6 B (8-14 m/s). A SAR image from 17 August 1997 is chosen.

Fig. 1. Wind rose from Hellisøy light house, for the period January 1993 through December 1998. Wind speed is given in Beaufort (B). SW1 indicates the most typical wind direction (and corresponding speed). This wind direction occur with a frequency of 21.5% of the time.

Fig. 2. A SatWind1 product. 17-08-97 with winds from the south (frequency 21.5%). The SAR extracted wind speed was averagedly 8-8.5m/s with a maximum value of 10-11m/s. From Hellisøy (indicated by a circle), an average wind speed of 7.6m/s was measured, with a maximum value of about 10.3m/s during a 6 hour period. The weather maps indicated a wind of 7.5m/s. In this case the local variation of the wind speed in the SAR image is small, except in the fjords where low wind speed areas cause some dark slicks.

In addition to the SAR wind speed and wind energy maps, the customer may extract profiles from the wind maps (the SatWind products will be delivered both as a hard-copy and on CD-rom). An example of a wind energy profile is shown in Figs.8-9.

The SatWind2 product:

The 5 most typical wind directions (total frequency 78.8%) are found using the wind rose from the local weather station (Fig.3). Winds are predominantly from the south (5-6 B = 8-14 m/s), south-east (3-4 B = 3-8 m/s), north (3-4 B = 3-8 m/s), north-west (3-4 B = 3-8 m/s) and south-west (3-4 B=3-8 m/s). The corresponding SAR images from 17-08-97, 08-08-96, 04-05-97, 21-09-97 and 15-02-96 are chosen. These are displayed below. A customer will in this case be given the opportunity to choose a 3 or 5 image product, SatWind2A or SatWind2B, covering 68.2% or 78.8% of the wind direction situations, respectively.

Fig. 3. Wind rose from Hellsøy light house, for the period January 1993 through December 1998. Wind speed is given in Beaufort (B).

SatWind2A(B)-1, SatWind2A(B)-2, SatWind2A(B)-3, SatWind2B-4 and SatWindB-5, indicate the most typical wind directions (and corresponding speeds). These wind directions occur with a total frequency of 78.8% of the time.

Fig. 4. The SatWind2A(B)-1. The SAR image is from 17-08-97 with winds from the south (frequency 21.5%). The SAR extracted wind speed was averagely 8 - 8.5 m/s with a maximum value of 10 - 11 m/s. From Hellisøy (indicated by a circle), an average wind speed of 7.6 m/s was measured, with a maximum value of about 10.3 m/s during a 6 hour period. The weather maps indicated a wind of 7.5 m/s. In this case the local variation of the wind speed in the SAR image is small, except in the fjords where low wind speed areas cause some dark slicks.

Fig.5. The SatWind2A(B)-2: 10-11-96 with winds from the south-east (frequency 17.9%). The SAR extracted wind speed was averagely 4.0 m/s with a maximum value of 9-10 m/s (are of large variability). From Hellisøy (indicated by a circle), an average wind speed of 6.1 m/s was measured, with a maximum value of about 8.0 m/s during a 6 hour period. The weather maps indicated a wind of 10.0 m/s.

Fig.6. The SatWind2A(B)-3: 04-05-97 with winds from the north (freq. 17.5%). The SAR extracted wind speed was averagely 3.5 m/s with a maximum value of 6.5 -7m/s. From Hellisøy (ind. by a circle), an average wind speed of 6.2 m/s was measured, with a maximum value of about 8.2 m/s during a 6 hour period. The weather maps indicated a wind of 10.0 m/s. There are some low wind speed areas along the the southern-most part of the coast seen in the SAR image.

Fig.7. The SatWind2B-4: 21-09-97 with winds from the north-west (frequency 11.3%). The SAR extracted wind speed was averagely 6 m/s with a maximum value of 8.5 m/s. From Hellisøy (indicated by a circle), an average wind speed of 4.6 m/s was measured, with a maximum value of about 7.5 m/s during a 6 hour period. The weather maps indicated a wind of 7.5 m/s. The local wind variations are small, however the wind speeds are a little higher in the northern parts compared to the southern parts of the SAR image.

Fig. 8. The SatWind2B-5: 15-02-96 with winds from south-west (frequency 10.6%). The SAR extracted wind speed was averagely 5.9 m/s with a maximum of 8.9 m/s. From Hellisøy (indicated by a circle), an average wind speed of 1.6 m/s was measured, with a maximum value of 2.4 m/s during a 6 hour period. The weather maps indicated a wind of 10 m/s. The wind energy profile along the white line is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. A profile displaying wind energy (Watt/m^2) along the white line (pixel number) indicated in the wind energy map from Fig.8. The spike at approximately 50km is caused by a ship.

4. Limitations of the SAR

The ideal situation is to be able to use the SAR imagery to retrieve the spatial variation of the probability density function (PDF) of the wind speed. However, this cannot be retrieved from a limited number of SAR images such as will be used in the products SatWind1 and SatWind2A(B). Therefore, local meteorological data (wind roses have to be used to find days with typical wind directions and speeds. Corresponding SAR images will then give examples of spatial wind variations for such a (typical) day. This is a limitation of the SAR, and is also partly due to data cost.

In coastal areas the land-sea-circulation contributes significantly to the local wind speed. This diurnal variation will not be seen in the SAR images, due to the satellite orbit (descending at approximately 10.50UTC, ascending at 21.30UTC). The evening pass might catch the onset of the land-sea wind, while sea breeze in the early afternoon will not be imaged at all.

Due to limitations in coverage and current prices, SAR imagery will not give an accurate description of all the different situations occurring at a site and it will not provide a basis for statistical analysis. What the SAR offers is an addition to traditional information (scattered in situ data and models). The SAR product will give an indication of spatial variations of wind on a local scale (400 m).

5. Data validation

5.1 Data, calibration and wind extraction

The examples of a product described in this report are taken from a region covering south-western Norway. This was due to the fact that NERSC already possessed several SAR scenes from this region, and the project did not allow for new data to be purchased. However, the methodology is transferable to other regions, for potential expansion of the product in the future.

Available data

A total number of 28 ERS-1/2 SAR scenes have been used together with corresponding Hindcast data, weather maps and wind data from Helligsøy and Slotterøy light houses. The available data are listed below.

Table 1. In addition to continuous wind data from Helligsøy and Slotterøy, the following data were used in the project

<u>Date</u>	<u>ERS SAR scenes</u>		<u>Hindcast</u>	<u>Weather map</u>
	<u>UTC</u>	<u>Orbit-Frame</u>	<u>UTC</u>	<u>UTC</u>
960126	21:28	23707-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960203	10:49	23815-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
960214	21:31	23979-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960215	21:31	04306-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960309	10:49	24316-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
960405	21:28	24709-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960406	21:28	05036-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960413	10:49	24817-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
960622	10:49	25819-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
960623	10:49	06146-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
960704	21:31	06310-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960719	21:28	26212-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960727	10:49	26320-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
960808	21:31	06811-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
960901	10:49	07148-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
960912	21:31	07312-1215	18:00, 24:00	21:00
961006	10:49	07649-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
961110	10:49	08150-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
961215	10:49	08651-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970119	10:49	09152-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970223	10:49	09653-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970330	10:49	10154-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970504	10:49	10655-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970608	10:49	11156-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970713	10:49	11657-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970817	10:49	12158-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
970921	10:49	12659-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00
971130	10:49	13661-2374	06:00, 12:00	09:00

5.2 Calibration and extraction of wind from SAR

An optimal wind speed estimate from the so-called C band models depends on the radiometric capabilities of the SAR to reproduce the normalized radar cross section (NRCS). An accurate calibration of the raw SAR data is necessary, and this is performed according to specifications given by *Laur et al.* [1997]. In particular the images are corrected for analogue-to-digital (ADC) conversion power loss. This power loss is caused by saturation in the binary representation of the radar signal and it is important to correct for this in cases of high radar return, i.e. high wind speed, in the image.

The wind speed is retrieved from the radar backscatter using a C band model. The CMOD IF2, developed at the Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer (IFREMER), is today used operationally for retrieval of wind field from the ERS-2 Wind Scatterometer (WSC) [*Quilfen*, 1995]. CMOD IF2 is empirically tuned to in situ measurements, and retrieves the wind field with an uncertainty of ± 2 m/s in wind speed and $\pm 20^\circ$ in the wind direction for the WSC. The CMOD IF2 has been shown to be applicable to the SAR with the same uncertainty on wind speed down to a resolution of at least 400 m [*Furevik and Korsbakken*, 1999]. A disadvantage of the SAR is the wind direction that is needed as an input to the model. The wind direction can in approximately 50% of the cases be estimated from signatures in the SAR image. These signatures can be lee effects of land or signatures of atmospheric roll vortices or Langmuir cells. In other cases the wind direction can be taken from meteorological weather stations along the coast, or from the Hindcast database of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute, or any other local wind models. It should be noted that an error in wind direction of 90° , which is the worst case, will result in an error in wind speed of 2 m/s for low winds and up to more than 10 m/s for strong winds. However, for strong winds the variation in local wind direction is little and in almost all these cases it is possible to locally verify the measured wind direction with signatures in the SAR images.

After the SAR images are calibrated, the wind field is retrieved. The wind speeds extracted from the SAR images in this project are validated as described in Section 3.1. One input value for the wind direction is used for each image. The resulting wind speed matrices are then transformed into matrices of wind energy (energy flux) by applying the formula

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{air} V^3$$

where E (W/m^2) is the energy flux, ρ_{air} is the density of the air and V is the wind speed. The results are shown in Section 3.2 using a colour scale to enhance the variations. The air density has a value of $1.225 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ at standard pressure and a temperature of 15°C .

5.3 Validation

The SAR extracted wind speeds were first validated by comparing against wind speed measurements from Hellisøy and local weather maps (Table 2). The input wind directions in the CMOD model were taken from Hellisøy. The wind extracted from the SAR imagery were averaged in both a 10×10 km and a 20×20 km box west of Hellisøy (see Fig.10). In addition, the maximum wind speed values in these boxes were noted (Table 2). In the cases where no SAR extracted winds are noted, the SAR imaged contained mostly land and very little sea area, making it difficult to place the boxes where wind values should be extracted for validation.

Fig. 10. The SAR wind speed map (example from 22-06-96). The boxes indicates the sub-areas where wind was extracted.

Table 2. Wind data from SAR, Hellisøy and weather maps. The *a* or *d* at the end of the orbit number indicates ascending or descending pass. Wind direction input for the CMOD model is taken from Hellisøy (except for 960704 where Hellisøy is outside SAR image, and the weather map was used). The two wind values in each column indicate mean and max values (val. from Hellisøy are averaged over 10 minutes, and the maximum is the highest value for a 6 hour period). The wind from SAR is extracted both for a 10×10 km and a 20×20 km box outside Hellisøy (Fig.10).

Date	ERS SAR					In situ (Hellisøy)			Weather maps	
	Orbit	Frame	Time UTC	Speed [m/s] 10km	Speed [m/s] 20km	Time UTC	Speed [m/s]	Dir.	Speed [m/s]	Dir.
960126	23707a	1215	21:28	-	-	22:00	5.2/7.2	32	7.5	70
960203	23815d	2374	10:49	9.2/12.7	9.0/15.6	11:00	5.5/9.6	1	5.0	355
960215	04306a	1215	21:31	5.9/8.9	6.6/10.9	22:00	1.6/2.4	238	10.0	280
960309	24316d	2374	10:49	2.7/4.6	3.1/7.7	11:00	3.1/3.9	86	5.0	170
960406	05036a	1215	21:28	-	-	22:00	1.9/2.2	70	2.5	110
960413	24817d	2374	10:49	0.0/1.6	0.0/3.4	11:00	2.7/3.5	269	2.5	170
960622	25819d	2374	10:49	9.8/12.1	9.6/12.1	11:00	14.7/19.4	339	12.5	350
960623	06146d	2374	10:49	5.1/7.0	5.0/7.0	11:00	8.5/10.3	321	5.0	315
960704	06310a	1222	21:31	4.9/7.2	5.0/9.0	-	-	-	5.0	190
960719	26212a	1215	21:28	-	-	22:00	4.4/5.9	189	5.0	200
960727	26320d	2374	10:49	9.7/12.3	9.7/12.6	11:00	9.3/11.8	234	12.5	200
960808	06811a	1215	21:31	3.4/6.1	3.6/7.4	22:00	4.3/5.2	146	5.0	170
960901	07148d	2374	10:49	1.3/3.9	1.7/5.4	11:00	2.9/4.0	211	5.0	200
960912	07312a	1215	21:31	10.4/13.7	10.4/15.7	22:00	8.9/14.2	7	12.5	30
961006	07649d	2374	10:49	9.3/12.7	9.3/15.2	11:00	10.2/11.8	225	12.5	225
961110	08150d	2374	10:49	4.8/9.3	3.9/10.4	11:00	6.1/8.0	113	10.0	225
961215	08651d	2374	10:49	7.6/12.9	7.0/12.9	11:00	2.7/7.1	27	7.5	90
970119	09152d	2374	10:49	1.2/5.8	2.7/10.8	11:00	2.6/3.0	102	5.0	350
970223	09653d	2374	10:49	19.2/22.1	19.3/22.3	11:00	16.2/18.9	196	15.0	180
970330	10154d	2374	10:49	10.0/13.0	10.7/13.7	11:00	9.3/12.2	243	12.5	260
970504	10655d	2374	10:49	3.5/6.4	3.6/6.9	11:00	6.2/8.2	359	10.0	40
970608	11156d	2374	10:49	0.2/2.3	0.4/3.7	11:00	5.1/7.9	302	5.0	135
970713	11657d	2374	10:49	2.2/3.9	1.8/4.0	11:00	3.9/6.0	180	5.0	165
970817	12158d	2374	10:49	8.0/10.5	8.4/10.9	11:00	7.6/10.3	180	7.5	190
970921	12659d	2374	10:49	6.2/8.5	5.9/8.5	11:00	4.6/7.5	293	7.5	275
971130	13661d	2374	10:49	8.5/11.1	8.3/12.2	11:00	7.2/9.1	5	15.0	10

The values from Table 2 are illustrated in a scatter plot in Fig. 11. The results indicate that the SAR extracted wind speeds give a fairly good agreement with in situ data from Hellisøy and weather maps. In a recent work, Furevik and Korsbakken [1999] have shown that the SAR extracts wind with ± 2 m/s uncertainty in wind speed. The reason some of the values in Table 2 differ more than 2 m/s, may be that the wind measured at Hellisøy is not representative of the situation further out in the open ocean where the SAR wind speeds were obtained. The Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI) has indicated that the wind directions measured at Hellisøy may only be valid very locally, due to the local topography. A difference in time and location of SAR and in situ wind is a problem that usually has to be taken into account when comparing results.

The SAR is able to give general indications of spatial variations in the wind field. This is potentially very useful for wind mill siting, and two products, SatWind1 and SatWind2A(B), has therefore been developed based on a market survey and a workshop held at the Nansen Center (NERSC).

Fig. 11. A scatterplot illustrating the results from Table 2.

6. References

Furevik, B., and Korsbakken, E., Comparison of Synthetic Aperture Radar and Scatterometer derived wind speed during the ERS Tandem Phase, Submitted to *J. Geophys. Res.*, May 1999.

Laur, H., P. Bally, P. Meadows, P. J. Sanchez, B. Schaettler, E. Lopinto, Derivation of the backscattering coefficient σ_0 in ESA ERS SAR PRI products, Doc. *ES-TN-RS-PM-HL09*, issue 2, rev. 2, Eur. Space Res. Inst., Frascati, Italy, June 28, 1996.

Quilfen, Y., ERS-1 off-line wind scatterometer products, Technical report, Doc. *CI-EX-MUT-CD0000-03-IF*, issue 1.0, IFREMER, BP 70, 29280 Plouzane, France, 1995.

Appendix 2: Marketing plan

Marketing Plan

SatWind

by

Einar Bjorgo

30 July 1999

1. Background

1.1 Current performance

The current performance of TerraOrbit is relatively solid. However, the latest annual result available, from 1997, was negative (approximately Euro 4,800). During 1997 TerraOrbit was not an active company and it was not until spring 1998 that a new strategy and financial support was provided by the owner, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC). The contracts made in 1998 will ensure a positive financial result for the company for 1998. Many of the tasks carried out in the awarded contracts have a marketing character. In addition, the company has received free marketing through appearances on national TV and in national newspapers in 1998. When compared to our main competitors within the wind energy mapping industry, the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (in situ measurements, turnover for 1998 was approximately Euro 36 million) and Vector AS (the main private topographic modelling company in Norway, turnover for 1998 was approximately Euro 116,000), TerraOrbit's budget and result are very small. At the moment TerraOrbit has a staff of only one person, but the close co-operation with its owner, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), gives TerraOrbit access to NERSC staff and equipment. Our competitors products are already developed and used by the customers, and so our product, *SatWind*, must compete with existing, but not similar, products.

The current performance of products used to map wind conditions in coastal areas are mainly based on point measurements and mathematical modelling. Our product is still under development, and so no financial results have so far been generated. At the moment it needs to be assessed how many satellite images it will take to deliver a quality-product that customers will use in their decision-making process. The current performance of our product can not be directly compared to existing methods, as we intend to cover larger regions with continuous spatial information, and not point-data as traditional wind-measurements provide. The main competitors in this respect will be computer models. These are currently used in the area our product will cover. So far, these models have been preferred by governmental authorities due to its cost and quality. However, the input to these models can be discussed. It is our attention to also provide satellite-derived wind speeds as input to computer models to also model wind conditions over coastal land-zones. The preliminary product shows good potential for identifying and quantifying spatial variations in wind-energy over ocean surfaces. One of our competitors, Vector AS, has indicated that they are interested in using our product for input to their model.

1.2 Background analysis

Based on data from the Danish wind turbine association (www.windpower.dk), total global wind turbine sales for 1997 was approximately Euro 700 million. The main cost of setting up a wind mill is the turbine. Figures in the appendix illustrates the world-wide wind energy capacity in 1997, the world market in 1997 (upper bar represents Danish sales, while lower bar represents total market globally), and the annual growth rate of approximately 20% in the worlds wind power capacity. A quality product would thus have a relatively large market to operate in, even if the costs related to wind mapping are relatively modest (1-3% of total project budget), see the market survey below.

The current performance has been reached through implementation of well documented algorithms to derive wind speed from ERS SAR data covering the main area of focus for potential wind mill development in Norway: the west coast. This area has high potential for wind mill park establishment as the general wind conditions are favourable for wind mill development, and existing infrastructure such as road networks and power lines, are relatively well developed. Wind mill development is one of the key areas of interest for the Norwegian government and local, regional, and national power supply companies are very favourable towards developing wind mill parks along the Norwegian west coast.

The main external impact that could be beneficial to our product would be a substantial reduction in the cost of larger orders for archived ERS SAR images. That would improve the cost-efficiency of our product significantly. Another external impact would be policy issues regarding development of wind power plants along the Norwegian west coast.

A market survey has been carried out where 15 individual users representing various potential customers answered questions via telephone or fax. The results from this survey are provided in appendix A.

1.3 Summary of market survey

Potential customers currently identified for SatWind products are listed in appendix A. The overview below illustrates which areas the interviewed individuals in the market survey are interested in, and their affiliation. National means Norwegian territory. Currently, the main area of focus for national wind mill park development is along the Norwegian west coast.

Name	Organisation	Area of interest
Harald Birkeland	Norwegian Wind Power Association	National Norwegian west coast
Leif Dons	Fred Olsen Energy	Global United Kingdom Norwegian west coast
Endre Dingsør	Vindkraftprosjektering AS, Wind Power Association West	National Norwegian West Coast Representing 44 organisations/companies with interests along the Norwegian west coast
Arne Reidar Gravdahl	Vector AS	National Norwegian coast
Lars Helge Helning	Vetro Energo/Norwegian Wind Energy	Europe Kola Peninsula Norwegian coast
Lars Landberg	Risoe	Global Denmark Norwegian coast
Atle Venaas	Sotra Energi	Norwegian west coast
Joergen Hoejstrup	NEG-Micon	Global Denmark Norway
Lars Tallhaug	Kjeller Wind-Techniques	National
Jostein Matre	Bergen County Energy	Norwegian west coast
Tor Aamodt	Aanderaa Instruments	Norwegian west coast
Jacob Melting	Bergen College	Norwegian west coast
Ingvar Lauvik	Austevoll Energy	Norwegian west coast
Rigmor Fardal	Ulstein AS	Europe National
Helge Lode	Norwegian Wind Power Forum	National Norwegian west coast Currently representing more than 60 organisations /companies, but this number is increasing

All interviewed persons were made well aware of the limitations of the SatWind products prior to answering specific questions. Nevertheless, the overall result from the market survey was that these limitations are acceptable, and that SatWind has potential to be used as an add-on information source to existing products for planning of wind mill locations in coastal areas in general, and along the Norwegian west coast in particular.

The general attitude, was that SatWind must be available in hardcopy and digital format. A background description of the product be included, along with the hardcopy image. The digital part of the product should be available in standard data formats, such as TIF and GIF. This finding was also restated by the customers present at the workshop. TerraOrbit has now also decided to also add the actual data file as a digital product for implementation into existing GIS. The results from the market survey indicated that customers are willing to pay up to 6,000 Euro for a quality SatWind product.

1.4 Summary of workshop

The workshop held at the Nansen Center put focus on a detailed explanation on the limitations and advantages of SatWind. The potential customers were given a thorough description on how SatWind is produced, and found the product acceptable as an add-on product, even with its limitations. Minutes from the workshop are available at:

http://www.terraorbit.com/SatWind/satwind_workshop_minutes.htm

The potential users found the added value of continuous spatial coverage highly valuable, even though the temporal resolution is poor. The potential for using SatWind as an add-on product in combination with point measurements and numerical models, is, according to the present potential customers, of significant value.

1.5 Opportunities and options

The strengths of our business in the future would be the spatially continuous source of information the product provides. It is also well structured for inclusion in Geographic Information Systems (GIS).

Potential weaknesses of the product will be the statistical significance possible to achieve from the available ERS SAR scenes, i.e. the temporal resolution of 3 days between image acquisition, at best, is a factor 300 times coarser than what is produced from point-measurements today (average values every 10 minutes). Another weakness will be the cost of the product. As long as the images are priced by the European Space Agency (ESA) to Euro 1,200 per 100 by 100 km scene, the resulting multi-image based products might be too expensive for the users to purchase. The temporal resolution and doubts as to whether the SatWind product will be useful in practice also resulted in more than 50% of the respondents to our market survey, were negative about SatWind. Another threat to our product is the uncertainties related to where in Norway it will be allowed to build windmills and also how many windmills will be allowed built. There are political questions that have not yet been answered satisfactorily, and they represent a potential

limiting factor on our market. However, there is today a strong interest in building windmills in Norway, which is reflected in several interest organizations (e.g. Vindkraftforum Vest of Norsk Windkraftforum).

However, the opportunities to include the product in synergy with e.g. point-measurements in order to illustrate spatial variation of wind energy in the vicinity of a point-measurement are relatively good. A single scene can also be used as input to computer model case studies to assess the complexity of the wind conditions in a given area.

We will therefore assess how a product can be of value based on a few scenes, e.g. to illustrate and quantify the high frequency spatial changes in wind conditions along the coast, and compare this to in situ measurements. This will illustrate that in situ measurements should not be the only source of information taken into consideration in the early phases of a wind mill site assessment. It is of utmost importance to be able to provide a product that fits the financial resources of the customers, and SatWind should therefore be based on relatively few scenes. Of course, customers able to pay for more scenes will have the opportunity to receive an upgraded version of the SatWind product.

The main actions that are needed to tackle these obstacles are to assess in detail the quality of the product compared to in situ measurements. An important factor here will be how many images are needed in order to cover various types of applications. These applications will range from total coverage along the coast based on all archived SAR scenes in the area of interest, to single scene test studies e.g. for model inputs. It is assumed that ESA and Radarsat price policy will not change in the near future, and so the price for purchasing raw data might be a severely limiting factor.

2. Marketing objectives of the proposed product or service

2.1 Marketing objectives

Sales:

Objective: To sell 18 copies of the final product to various customers operating in the wind-power industry interested in wind-energy conditions along the Norwegian west coast and/or the general method and quality of our product. We believe this number is realistic as the region covered by our product is of direct interest for all the interviewed persons in the market survey. Two of the 15 individuals interviewed represent interest organisations, with a total number of members currently at 104, but growing. Thus, a total of $104+13=117$ potential customers' requirements were identified in the market survey. Since 46% of the answers in the market survey were positive to the SatWind products developed for the Norwegian west coast, including the limitations of the product, the total number of potential customers can be estimated to 46% of 117, i.e. 54 potential customers. TerraOrbit thus estimates that 1 of 3 potential customers ($54/3=18$), who are already in favour of SatWind along the Norwegian west coast, including its limitations, will purchase the product.

The product will be provided in three versions, SatWind1, SatWind2A, and SatWind2B. SatWind1 will be a less expensive and simpler product than SatWind2A&B. SatWind1 will be produced so as to target individual companies and users, while SatWind2 will be targeted towards governmental agencies and interest organisations.

We expect to sell five copies of SatWind1, and one copy of SatWind2A in 1999. In 2000 we expect SatWind1 to sell in eight copies, and SatWind2A to sell in two copies, while SatWind2B sell in two copies. This represents sales in-between an optimistic and a pessimistic scenario described in detail in section 2.2.

For the current product covering the Norwegian west coast, the wind direction used for SatWind1 occurs with a frequency covering 21.5% of the various wind conditions. SatWind2A covers approximately 68%, while SatWind2B covers approximately 78.8% of the various wind conditions. See wind rose in Figure 1 below for additional information.

Figure 1. Wind rose for Hellisoy indicating wind directions for the various SatWind products.

2.2 Financial objectives

The three different SatWind products will be priced like this: SatWind1 will be priced at Euro 500, SatWind2A at Euro 3,600, and SatWind2B at Euro 6000, respectively. SatWind1 will only be offered as a single-licence product. That is, the product can only be used by the particular customer, not by e.g. another division within the same department. SatWind2A&B however, will have a multi-use licence, so that all divisions within the same company, or all members of an interest-organisation can use the product. SatWind1 will consist of one scene selected to represent as close as possible the most typical wind condition for the area of interest. SatWind2A will include three scenes, each selected so as to represent as close as possible three typical wind conditions frequently occurring in the region of interest, while SatWind2B will consist of five scenes, each selected so as to represent as close as possible five typical wind conditions. Note that the scene in SatWind1 will be included in SatWind2A, and that the scenes in SatWind2A will be included in SatWind2B. Table 1 lists the two products, while table 2 and 3 lists the cost involved in producing SatWind1 and 2. Figure 2 illustrates what a hardcopy of SatWind1 could look like.

Table 1. Overview of SatWind1 and SatWind2 products.

Product	Licence	Number of images used	Energy image	Profile plot	Format
SatWind1	Single-user	1	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Hardcopy, CD-ROM, Interactive WWW
SatWind2	Multi-user	3 or 5	Yes (5)	Yes (5)	Hardcopy, CD-ROM, Interactive WWW

Table 2. SatWind1 budget.

Task	Cost (Euro)
Purchase of 1 satellite image	1,200
Labour, 3 days at Euro 600 each	1,800
Hard- and digital copy production	100
Total	3,100

The break-even level will thus be reached once we have sold seven copies of SatWind1 (Euro 3,500) at Euro 500 each.

Table 3. SatWind2 budget, based on 3 to 5 scenes.

Task	Cost (Euro)
Purchase of 3/5 satellite images	3,600/6,000
Labour, 10 days at Euro 600 each	4,500/7,500
Hard- and digital copy production	300/500
Total	8,400/14,000
Total, mean (50% 3 images, 50% 5 images)	11,200

Various break-even scenarios are thus possible for SatWind2. The break-even level for SatWind2A separately (Euro 8,400) will be reached once we have sold three copies of SatWind2A (Euro 10,800) at Euro 3,600 each. For SatWind2B separately, we will also need to sell three copies (Euro 18,000) at Euro 6,000 each, to reach the break-even point of Euro 14,000.

However, various combinations of SatWind1 and SatWind2A&B are possible. Since the images, and corresponding processing, of SatWind1 is included in SatWind2A&B, and SatWind2A is included in SatWind2B, a break-even level might e.g. be reached from selling one copy of SatWind2B (Euro 6,000), two copies of SatWind2A (Euro 7,200), and two copies of SatWind1 (Euro 1,000). This will ensure an income of Euro 14,200 which will pass the break-even level for SatWind2B (Euro 14,000). It is difficult to estimate how many SatWind2A products will be sold compared to SatWind2B. We therefore make a simple assumption that of all SatWind2 products, we will sell 50% of SatWind2A and 50% of SatWind2B. An “average” SatWind2 product will thus consist of 4 images, at a production cost of Euro 11,200.

Figure 2. Example of a SatWind1 product, from 17-08-97(or Part 1 of a SatWind2 product) with winds from the south (frequency 21.5%). The SAR extracted wind speed was on average 8 - 8.5 m/s with a maximum value of 10 - 11 m/s. From Hellisøy (indicated by a circle), an average wind speed of 7.6 m/s was measured, with a maximum value of about 10.

Two possible scenarios are described below, the first is an optimistic scenario, where we expect to sell 20 copies of SatWind1, and 3 copies of SatWind2A, and 3 copies of SatWind2B. The second scenario is a pessimistic scenario, where we expect to sell 5 copies of SatWind1, and zero copies of SatWind2.

If SatWind1 is sold in 20 copies, the income will be Euro 10,000. If SatWind2A and SatWind2B are sold in 3 copies each, the income will be Euro 28,800. The total income for the optimistic scenario will thus be Euro 38,800. For the pessimistic scenario, if SatWind1 is sold in only 5 copies, and SatWind2 is not sold at all, the total income will be Euro 2,500.

If the pessimistic scenario becomes true (only 5 customers are willing to pay, and only for the less expensive product), we should consider giving away the product for free. This would at least provide us with real feedback on how useful the product is in operational work. However, feedback on this will also be received through the user workshop to be arranged by NERSC.

3. Marketing strategy of the proposed product or service

3.1 Target market segments

Types of customers:

The targeted customers represent private industry and public agencies involved in wind power-plant development. We also intend to market the product towards interest-organisations, such as Western Norway Wind-Power Forum, and the Norwegian Wind-Power Forum. All targeted customers have high interest in potential wind mill development along the Norwegian west coast.

Needs and profiles:

These customers need reliable data to locate optimum sites for placing individual wind mills, but also information to develop policies for where to limit construction due to e.g. wildlife parks, or strong environmental impacts.

Based on the market survey it is clear that the customers need spatially continuous information on wind conditions. However, based on the cost-analysis it is clear that the product must fit into the rather limited budget used for wind information. The market segment will therefore be targeted with the above described SatWind1 and SatWind2 products. SatWind1 is designed to provide individual users, foremost private companies, with synergy information to the data they already have (in situ point measurements and/or modelling results). The interactive digital part of the product will improve quantification means and further demonstrate SatWinds usefulness as a synergy product. SatWind2 is intended more towards users who can afford a more expensive product, such as governmental agencies and major private companies. The added information compared to SatWind1 will be the additional information from variations wind conditions, listed as very important by the users themselves in the market-survey. Three or five images, one snapshot for each typical wind situation (see Figure 1), will be provided in SatWind2.

3.2 Differential advantage

The provision of continuous spatial information is the main advantage of our product. The maps can also relatively easily be implemented in GIS in order to assess where there are existing road networks and power transport infrastructure. Such parameters are included in one of our competitors products (topographic modelling results overlaid road networks). These are important parameters to keep the investments low and thus potential profits higher for the power-plant companies.

We will focus on the synergy effect with point-measures and that our product can show relatively large local variations in this coastal area. We thus want the customers to choose our product as an add-on to existing products, but used so as to maximise the potential benefit in choosing one location instead of another. Point-measurements can never be replaced, but in deciding where to put them, our product can be beneficial. Another benefit is that our product can be provided within a relatively short time frame. Since the products are pre-defined, SatWind1 and SatWind2, these can be delivered to the customers within 24 hours, or within two days if the existing stock of hardcopies and CD-ROMs is empty. This is a differential advantage when assessing an area where no point measurements are available. In situ data are normally collected over one year, see market-survey, and so our low-level product will have a differential advantage in such areas.

Another differential advantage will be the easy-to-use interactive interface. The user interface will be through an HTML coded website and so energy profiles will be extracted without much technical know-how on how to integrate the energy and plot this in a separate software program. This website will be accessible online, but also directly from the CD-ROM. SatWind will be user friendly. This is especially important when the customers are e.g. politicians, bureaucrats, and land owners without expertise knowledge in wind mapping.

4. Marketing mix

4.1 Product or service

We will provide a product for mapping wind energy conditions along the Norwegian west coast. We must have a quality controlled cost/benefit competitive product. The product will consist of a hardcopy wind atlas with images of individual SAR wind-energy scenes used. In addition we will include the relationship between satellite-derived wind-speed and in situ derived wind-speed from two stations belonging to the Norwegian Meteorological Society to assess the quality of the product. We will also list which wind-directions are used to process the individual scenes. An interactive digital version of the hardcopy will be provided on CD-ROM in HTML

coding for easy use through web-browsers such as Netscape and Explorer. The users can themselves pick a profile on the wind energy map, and automatically view the variations in wind energy over the distance from which the profile was picked.

More specifically the products will be SatWind1 and SatWind2A&B, also described in section 2. SatWind1 will be based on one SAR scene representative for a typical wind condition. This product is designed to be of relatively low cost, but will still contribute to complementary information on the spatial variation of wind conditions over the area of interest. SatWind2A&B will be similar to SatWind1, but will be based on 3 and 5 SAR scenes, respectively. The images typical for each situation will be chosen based on weather maps and in situ time series of wind measurements. These products will be more expensive, and include energy maps for all individual scenes.

In general, the location of the SAR scene can vary according to customer requirements. Usually, one scene should be enough to cover an area of interest for the customer. If several different locations are interesting, several scenes have to be purchased. The current product covers the Norwegian west coast, since this is a high priority area for potential wind mill development. The customers described in this marketing plan are also highly interested in this area.

SatWind1 will be provided as a single-licence product only, while SatWind2 will be provided with a multi-licence. SatWind1 is thus targeted towards private companies, while SatWind2 is targeted towards interest organisations and governmental agencies. To each of the three products, SatWind1, SatWind2A and SatWind2B, a technical support service is included. See also table 1, section 2.

4.2 Price

SatWind1 is priced at Euro 500, SatWind2A is priced at Euro 3,600, and SatWind2B is priced at Euro 6,000. See also table 2 and 3, section 2.

4.3 Promotion

The product has been promoted through:

- a newsstory on national TV (TV2, 22 March 1998).
- in various newspapers:
 - Aftenposten 17 March 1998, Aftenposten is the largest subscription newspaper and the third largest single copies newspaper in Norway. Circulation number: approximately 500 000
 - Bergensavisen 18 March 1998, circulation number approximately 31 000
- a talk given at a conference for the regional wind-power industry (Vindkraftforum Vest), 9 February (28 participants)

- a poster presentation at a conference for the national wind-power industry (Norsk Vindkraftforum) 17 February. This conference was attended by 42 people, and the secretary for the minister of oil&energy was a keynote speaker.
- A scientific article on the methodology has also been accepted for publication as a cover story in International Journal of Remote Sensing.
- workshop held at the Nansen Center 26 April for targeted customer groups.
- Product information also is accessible through TerraOrbit's web-site: www.terraorbit.com.
- The final product will be featured in advertisements in special wind energy magazines.

Moreover, copies of the news-video, newspaper articles and the scientific article will be sent potential customers accompanied by a detailed description of the product.

The goal is to promote the product to all key players in the wind-energy business along the west coast of Norway, offices involved in wind-power policy, as well as other key players in the wind-energy business operating elsewhere. An additional goal is to promote the product within national governmental agencies, such as the Ministry of Oil and Energy, and the Ministry of Environment.

A total number of 41 potential customers (targets for promotion activities) have been identified. These are listed in Appendix A.

4.4 Distribution goals

The product will be distributed in hardcopy form and as a CD-ROM through regular mail. The hardcopy will consist of a wind energy image with continuous spatial information on the wind energy over ocean/lakes. In addition, the results from comparing satellite-derived wind to in situ derived wind will be presented as a scatterogram with corresponding statistical information. The CD-ROM will contain an interactive application programmed in HyperText Markup Language (HTML) and Java. Through their own interface web-browser (e.g. Netscape or Explorer) the customers can interactively extract wind energy profiles for their area of interest. The web-address for this service is: <http://sofia.nrsc.no>. Individual images will also be possible to extract from the CD-ROM for inclusion in their own GIS systems and/or in reports. The file formats will depend on user requirements, and can be e.g. MapInfo, ERMapper, ArcView, .gif or .jpg. The information available on CD-ROM will also be provided on a password protected TerraOrbit web-site. In addition, we can send out the digital product on e-mail or ftp.

4.5 Services (internal support)

All support services will be available through TerraOrbit. However, technical support will be routed through the Nansen Center for efficient problem solving.

4.6 Staff

The staff currently involved in the product is

NERSC: Ola M. Johannesse
 Stein Sandven
 Heidi Espedal
 Birgitte Rugaard Furevik
TerraOrbit: Einar Bjorgo

5. Action plans

These are the actions meant to take into effect after this developing and marketing project is finished.

Action	Responsible	Deadline	Cost (Euro)
Sales and marketing	Einar Bjorgo, TerraOrbit	Implemented, continuous action, sales starts in week 16/99	80/hr
Technical support	Heidi Espedal, NERSC	Continuous, start week 16/99	80/hr

6. Budget

The table below shows how the marketing activity is budgeted.

Activity	Cost (Euro)
Participation at conferences	3,000
Copying of 40 videos	400
Ads in wind magazines	600
Writing of popular science articles for wind industry magazines	2,000
Total	6,000

Revenues: Euro 29,300

Expenditures: Euro 20,400 (cost of producing one copy of SatWind2B, and derived versions to SatWind1 and SatWind2A)

Profits: Euro 8,900

Cash-flow: We expect to sell five copies of SatWind1 and one copy of SatWind2A in 1999, thus expecting a cash-flow of Euro 6,100 this year. In 2000 we expect SatWind1 to sell in eight copies, and SatWind2A&B to sell in 2 copies each, thus totalling Euro 23,200 for 2000 and Euro 29,300 altogether. See also the optimistic and pessimistic scenarios outlined in section 2.2. The numbers listed for cash-flow represent sales in-between the optimistic and pessimistic scenarios. Since SatWind1 and SatWind2A are parts of SatWind2B, the main expenditure is from producing SatWind2B (Euro 14,000). However, additional expenditures comes from producing the “linked” SatWind1 and SatWind2A products. This expenditure is related to the digital copy production and web-interface. This cost is estimated to Euro 100 for SatWind1 and Euro 300 for SatWind2A, totalling Euro 400. Also, the marketing activity must be included (Euro 6,000). The total expenditures are thus estimated to Euro 20,400.

7. Organisational implications

This is the first time such a product is introduced to the wind-energy market. At present, and in the near future, the market is rather limited (Norwegian West coast) and so the organisational structure of NERSC and TerraOrbit will not change except for individual persons’ responsibility to follow up on their assigned tasks.

Appendix A: Potential customers

The following specific potential customers have so far been identified:

1. Harald Birkeland, Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate
2. Geir Fuglseth, Statkraft
3. Leif Dons, Fred Olsen Energy AS
4. Endre Dingsør, Vindkraftprosjektering AS
5. Arne Reidar Gravdahl, Vector AS
6. Lars Helge Helning, Vetro Energo/Norwegian Wind Energy
7. Lars Landberg, Risoe
8. Atle Venaas, Sotra Energy
9. Joergen Hoeistrup, NEG-Micon
10. Lars Tallhaug, Kjeller Wind-techniques
11. Jostein Matre, Bergen County Energy
12. Tor Aamodt, Aanderaa Instruments
13. Jacob Melting, Bergen College
14. Lin Gan, Center for International Climate and Environmental Research
15. Anne Gro Ullaland, Hordaland Municipality
16. Froedis Ones, Sund County
17. Jan Ove Bratseth, Grotle Landowners Association
18. Ingvar Lauvik, Austevoll Energy
19. Rigmor Fardal, Ulstein AS
20. Terje Aarsand, Norwegian Tourist Association
21. Kjersti Linge, Western Norway Energy Economy
22. Soren Krohn, Danish Wind Turbine Manufacturers Association
23. Helge Lode, Norwegian Wind Power Forum
24. Reidar Gjoesok, Gjoesok Project
25. J. Koloen, Boemlo County
26. B.T. Iversen, Myklebust-Group
27. Arild Knutsen, Shell Norway
28. Ole Vidar Lunde, Fitjar Power Company
29. Gjermund Mortveit, Haugesund Energy
30. Odd Nes, Ytre Fjordane Power Association

31. Knut M. Olsen, Sogn og Fjordange Municipality
32. Harald Oscarser, Statkraft Engineering
33. Aksel Skjervheim, Bergen County
34. Sigmund Skjold, Sunnhordland Power Company
35. Arild Skretting, Lyse Power
36. Kjell Stalheim, Stord Energy
37. Arne Steen, Nordhordaland Power Company
38. Sverre Oevrebotten, Asplan Viak Bergen AS
39. Dagfinn Aasen, Askoey Energy AS
40. Iver Nordseth, Smoela County
41. Kjell Ove Hjelmeland, Western Norway Planning Group

Market survey

(i) Type of institute

Interest organisation	20%
Private company	50%
Governmental agency	30%

Two of the institutes represented in this survey are Danish and interested in the method in general, not the direct results from the area along the West coast of Norway, while the rest is directly interested in mapping the wind potential on the West coast of Norway.

(ii) Information need regarding planning of wind-power plants

- *What is your connection to the wind power industry*

Project engineering&development	44%
Operations of wind-mills	19%
Consulting	37%

- *Information need during planning period*

Active involvement in wind-mapping 88%

How important are the following parameters regarding wind-mapping (1: less important, 2: important, 3: very important).

	1	2	3
Spatial variation	0%	12%	88%
Daily variation	25%	50%	25%
Monthly variation	38%	12%	50%
Seasonal variation	12%	12%	76%
Annual variation	12%	24%	64%

- *What is your present source of information for mapping wind conditions*

	% users	own	from others
Point measurements	100%	70%	30%
Synoptic weather obs.	50%	0%	100%
Pressure-field maps	12%	0%	100%
Wind-models	62%	43%	57%

- *Time series for wind measurements*

2.4.1 How long time period does a typical data collection last?

1 year	76%
1-3 years	12%
3-5 years	12%

- *What is the mean data capture frequency?*

10 minutes 100%

- *How many point-measurements do you perform on each site?*

1 63%

1-5 25%

1-10 12%

All answers stressed that the number of point measurements is strongly dependent on the topography.

- *Is today's information access sufficient for cost-efficient localisation of wind-mills?*

Yes 29%

No 71%

If no, what improvements are needed?

- More data along the coast
- More accurate data
- More detailed data
- Improved resolution in wind-models
- Improved global data
- Information from satellites

(iii) Costs

- *What are the typical costs regarding planning and construction of wind power plants?*

930 Euro per kW delivery potential 66%

950 Euro per kW delivery potential 17%

1100 Euro per kW delivery potential 17%

- *What is the percentage cost spent on mapping wind conditions for a wind power plant development process?*

1-2% 50%

2-3% 25%

3-4% 25%

In general, the resources used for mapping wind conditions vary between approximately Euro 12,000-25,000, according to the interviewed personnel.

- *Is today's cost acceptable compared to the information you receive?*

Yes 63%

No 37%

(iv) Potential improvements

- *Continuous spatial coverage*

Would your organisation be willing to spend financial resources in order to receive continuous spatial wind information over ocean and large lakes along the coast? The continuous spatial coverage is based on satellite image "snapshots" dating back to 1991. The revisit period between each snapshot is 3 days at the best. This spatially continuous information can be used to retrieve wind speed and wind energy in a profile along the coast, analyse local (400 by 400 m cells) variations in wind conditions, and plan where to place point measurements for more detailed time series analyses.

The answers to this question is summarised below in positive responses and negative responses.

Positive remarks totalled 46% of the answers, these can be divided into:

- SatWind has potential as synergy information on where to continue with field measurements 27%
- Yes, SatWind is interesting, even if coarse temporal resolution 19%

Negative remarks totalled 54% of the answers, these can be divided into:

- In doubt if our method will be useful in practice 27%
- Too coarse temporal frequency 27%

(v) Future perspective

- *How many wind power plants do you expect to be in the construction process or finished within the region of your interest?*

in the next 1-3 years

0 (Western Norway)	13%
30 (Danish region)	12%
3000 individual mills (global distributors)	12%

in the next 3-5 years

2-3 (Western Norway)	13%
5-10 (Western Norway)	14%
20-30 (Danish region)	24%
8000 individual mills (global distributors)	12%

Here it was noted that for Western Norway this is still very much a political issue, and so the numbers are very insecure. Many of the people interviewed did not want to speculate in quantifying this, as the framework for such development is still not in place. Not even the governmental agencies could give more certain answers regarding the planned development process.

(vi) Conclusion from market survey

Based on the market survey, SatWind has a potential to be used as an add-on, or synergy, product within the wind energy business. It is however, important to take into account the negative remarks and design the product so that it will be of sufficient quality for being sold, and to have a price that can realistically be fitted into the budget of mapping wind conditions. We will focus on the synergy effect between in situ point measurements and their temporal resolution, and to use the product as input to topographic models for assessing realistic case studies.

From the market analysis, one can not retrieve different patterns in information-requirements from the three different user groups (interest organisations, private companies, governmental agencies). This can possibly be because the development and planning of wind power plants along the Norwegian coast are still in an early phase. It could also be attributed to similar information needs, and that the developers know that they have to take various environmental aspects into consideration when planning a windmill site.

Based on the market-survey, the potential customers indicate that they use approximately Euro 12,000-25,000 on wind-mapping during the decision-making process on where to locate a wind-mill. This cost varies greatly, but in general it is estimated that the customers use 1-3% of the total budget for collecting information on the wind-conditions.

The rule-of-thumb is that the total budget is approximately Euro 900 per kW the wind-mill is designed to deliver.

Given that our product is designed to provide complementary information to point-measurements and mathematical models, it is not realistic that the customers will use more than 25% of their budget on our product, i.e. 25% of the 1-3% spent on wind mapping. The advantages with SatWind have already been described. It is also a new product that might draw attention because the customers simply would like to assess the usefulness of this product themselves. It is thus concluded that the customers can be willing to pay up to Euro 6,000 for a quality product.

Appendix B: Images

Appendix C: Addendum to marketing plan

Addendum to Marketing Plan
SatWind

by

Einar Bjorgo

This addendum to the Marketing Plan submitted by e-mail on 3 March 1999, is based on the findings from the user workshop held at the Nansen Center in Bergen, 26 April.

Several questions were raised by JRC/CEO in an e-mail from Nina Costa dated 22 February. These issues have been separately dealt with and answered on e-mail by Heidi Espedal dated 26 February 1999. However, a few general comments still remained to be answered based on the findings from the workshop. The draft final report including Technical Report and Marketing Plan will be submitted on 26 May 1999. Please keep in mind that this project from the very beginning was designed to focus on the test-area outside western Norway. It is this area we have received SAR imagery from, and it is this area that the final products have been developed for. However, the methodology is transferable to other regions, for potential expansion of the product in the future.

Below follows answers to specific issues, identified in e-mail from Nina Cost as of 22 February. These answers are based on findings from the user workshop.

Is wind information based on singular SAR scenes of commercial interest?

According to the users present at the workshop, SatWind 1&2 are of commercial interest, in spite of the lack of temporal averaging.

Since SAR imagery is a simple snapshot of the wind conditions acquired during similar times of day (ascending/descending passes), NERSC and TerraOrbit will select the imagery closest to these situations. This was acceptable by the users present. The representative from the Norwegian Wind Power Association also pointed out that the standard meteorological stations should not always be assumed correct, and the additional information provided by the snapshot SAR imagery derived products would be of interest. The identification and visualization of e.g. wind fronts and turbulent areas would be of high interest for the users, according to this representative for the Norwegian Wind Power Association. The users thus found the relative (as opposed to absolute) information to be of commercial value.

Since SatWind 1&2 will present a spatial continuous snapshot of a near annual average wind situation (SatWind 1), as well as four typical wind situations (SatWind2) the typical features possible to extract have commercial value, according to the users present.

Main target group

TerraOrbit has discussed with Vector AS the possibility of using SatWind 1&2 as input to their models. For the moment Vector is not interested in using SAR as input to their model, as they do not have the staff available to refine their model software. Vector is currently under contract to deliver several inland wind-model results for other potential wind-site areas in Norway. However, the product can potentially be included in the future.

Based on the positive response from the users at the workshop, and the negative response from Vector, it was decided not to change the target group.

How products should be sold

In order to make sure that the product is as cheap as possible, the users were not interested in operating through “middle-men”, but preferred to act directly with TerraOrbit. It is thus our impression that the best strategy for marketing and selling this specialized product is through TerraOrbit. Especially because of the close relationship with the product developer, the Nansen Center.

The product should be provided in hardcopy, and on CD-ROM in specific formats required by customers. A product version with access through Internet was also found interesting. This will be the Java-interface developed by NERSC/TerraOrbit. Such an interface should be password protected for the specific products.

The issue raised by Volkar Wissman regarding copyright problems if the product is delivered on CD-ROM is a non-issue. Thousands of multimedia and image products are today delivered on CD-ROM. The music industry does obviously deliver almost all their products on CD-ROM. Yes, the products can be copied, but this will be illegal according to the copyright form each customer must sign. This issue is not restrictive for our product. All digital files on CD-ROM can be copied. Obviously all hardcopies can also be copied, but this will be illegal too, if it is distributed to persons and organizations not included in the copyright agreement.

Minutes from workshop

Below are the minutes from the SatWind user workshop. These minutes are also available on the Internet at:
http://www.terraorbit.com/SatWind/satwind_workshop_minutes.htm

Minutes from CEO SatWind workshop 26 April 1999

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway

Number of participants: 16

Participants represented the user community (interest organizations and authorities) and research community (NERSC and University of Bergen).

Program 09:30-12:00 hrs:

1. Welcome: Ola M. Johannessen, NERSC
2. Introduction: Einar Bjorgo, TerraOrbit
3. Use of satellite imagery to estimate wind energy: Heidi Espedal, NERSC
4. Various sources for wind energy information: Jorgen Hojstrup, NEG Micon, Denmark
5. Use of satellite imagery in numerical models: Oyvind Breivik, NERSC
6. Wind modelling at University of Bergen: Anne Sandvik and Idar Barstad, Geophysics Department, University of Bergen

1.

Ola M. Johannessen welcomed the participants and presented a brief background on the idea of using synthetic aperture radar (SAR) satellite imagery for wind energy mapping. The participants received a background paper published in ESA Quarterly Journal by O.M. Johannessen and E. Korsbakken. Johannessen underscored the necessity of combining satellite data with numerical models.

2.

Einar Bjorgo gave a brief background for this workshop, presented the program, and encouraged participants from the research community to minimize technical term in order to not exclude representatives from the users in the discussions. He encouraged questions and comments during and between each presentation.

3.

Heidi Espedal presented the technical background for how SAR data can be used to estimate wind energy. She stressed that the products so far are very basic, and that more advanced SAR derived products including numerical models, could be expected in the future. The main benefits from SAR is the rapid turnaround time for spatially continuous wind energy information. Jorgen Hojstrup commented that wind speeds above 10 m/s require non-standard extra strength wind mills. Endre Dingsor from the Norwegian Wind Power Association commented that it is very important to include information on how the wind speed varies with height. He also commented that SAR derived products could be very useful in comparizons to wind atlases to highlight where wind turbulens (as derived from SAR imagery) is often present. Ola M. Johannessen commented on the potential for using SAR in development countries, such as along the Indian west coast. SAR data can also be compared to altimeter and scatterometer data for larger scale verification.

4.

Jorgen Hojstrup presented a talk on various sources for collecting wind energy information, including the utilization of satellite data. His company, NEG-Micon, covers approximately 25% of the world market for wind-mill development. Offshore wind mill parks have a great potential, and Denmark is planning extensive parks from year 2000 and 2001. Why is Denmark focusing on offshore wind mill parks?

- flat terrain
- higher windspeeds
- less turbulence
- enough space (land areas for wind mills are almost full)
- less complaints from neighbours (less NIMBY – Not In My Back Yard)

However, there are problems with offshore installations:

- less wind data available
- in situ measurements are very expensive
- the cost of setting up wind mills increases with the distance to shore

In general, highly accurate wind data are needed, as investors often require wind speed estimate accuracies within a few percent when judging potential clients.

Accessible wind data for potential offshore locations:

- commercial ship carriers
 - poorly calibrated
 - flow distortion
- light houses

- mostly not very reliable
- extrapolation to offshore often inaccurate
- meteorological stations along coastline
 - relatively few
- upper air data
 - output from models, re-analyse
 - long time series
 - geostrophic extrapolation to sea level
 - problem if stability is important, i.e. local circulation, sea ice, etc.
- in situ measurements
 - expensive
 - long delivery time
 - quality results
- satellite data
 - absolute accuracy not sufficient, can this be improved?
 - can spatial variations be correctly represented? Ola M. Johannessen commented positively on this using SAR
 - are time series long enough for statistical analyses?
 - major advantage: products can be delivered much more quickly than from e.g. in situ measurements
 - in situ data is needed when detailed info on area is collected

5.

Oyvind Breivik explained how various sources of satellite imagery could be included in numerical models. Scatterometers, altimeters, and SAR can all be included in numerical models. A potential application is through data assimilation:

analysis = forecast + observations

The forecast is produced from numerical models, while observations can be from in situ and satellite data.

6.

Anne Sandvik presented general potential uses of numerical models based on “clean” signals from large scale models, quality input parameters, and lastly inclusion of topography, friction, etc.. One will need statistics on historical data, simulation on scales that will truly take into consideration the effects of flow across mountains, and simulations that will resolve local fields.

Idar Barstad explained what the Geophysics Department at the University of Bergen currently work on regarding wind mapping. He focused on the use of frequency distributions of wind speed and direction, turbulence, and ice problems. Available data are scattered meteorological stations, re-analyzed numerical models, shorter in situ time series from various areas. He suggested co-operation within the areas of large scale wind climate data, numerical model simulations for various wind directions and stability inputs, nesting of numerical models down to 100 m resolution, validation of models e.g. as a master-thesis.

The workshop concluded on time at 12:00 hrs.

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